

An ecofriendly approach – A simple and clean synthesis in aqueous medium via supramolecular catalysis[†]

Madhulika Srivastava^a, Pratibha Rai^a, Snehlata Yadav^a, Bhartendu Pati Tripathi^a, Anu Mishra^a,
Jaya Singh^b and Jagdamba Singh^{*a}

^aEnvironmentally Benign Lab, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002,
Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dr.jdsau@gmail.com

^bL. R. P.G. College, Sahibabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract : An environmentally benign, readily available and cost effectiveness β -cyclodextrin serve as a good alternative to the expensive catalysts containing metals. Here we report a new approach for the synthesis of 3',3',6',6'-tetramethyl-3',4',6',7'-tetrahydrospiro[indoline-3,9'-xanthene]-1',2,8'(2'H,5'H)-trione, 3,3,6,6-tetramethyl-9-phenyl-3,4,5,6,7,9-hexahydro-1H-xanthene-1,8(2H)-dione and its derivatives using β -cyclodextrin.

Keywords : Supramolecular chemistry, β -cyclodextrin, water, dimedone, isatin.

Introduction

Water is always appear in spotlight^{1a} in organic synthesis due to its safer behaviour on environment and cost effectiveness^{1b}. Various reactions mentioned in literature have proven that water is the best solvent for solution phase chemistry^{1c} due to its idiosyncratic properties such as, easy availability high dielectric constant, non-toxic nature, easy handling and cost effectiveness^{1d}. It has been found that when water is used as a solvent, it increases the yield as well as selectivity for example in Mannich reaction^{1f}. In such cases when the reaction is unable to proceed efficiently in water, chemists make use of surfactants², phase transfer catalysts, etc. In this regards cyclodextrin stands as an important tool. Cyclodextrin works in a host-guest manner, its internal cavity is strongly hydrophobic and encourage the reagent to react and forms an inclusion complex with reagent. Some other impelling forces are Van der Waal forces, hydrophobic interaction, electronic factor and steric factors.

It is not surprising that biodynamic spirocyclic compounds have received greater attention in the field of organic synthesis as compared to heterocyclic compounds due to their wide spectrum qualities like being anticancer⁴,

antibacterial⁵, anticonvulsant⁶, antituberculosis⁷, pain relieving⁸, etc. A recent increase in the synthesis of spirocyclic compounds is due to their wide scale applications in the field of pharmacy, agriculture and production of biologically active products. These studies inspire and encourage us to synthesise spiro compound. Recently Yasumasa Hamada *et al.* synthesised spiro[4.5]cyclohexadienones, Chao-Guo Yan^{9a} and co-workers synthesised spiro[cyclopenta[b]-pyridine-4,20-indenes], AlesRuzicka *et al.* synthesised spiro-benzo[1,3]oxathioles^{9b} and in connection with our recent work^{9c}, we again attempted the establishment of a new synthetic strategy for the synthesis of spiro compounds (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of target compounds.

Results and discussion

Initially we took a mixture of isatin and dimedone¹⁰ in water (25 ml) containing a round flask. The reaction com-

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

Scheme 2. Plausible mechanism of the desired compounds.

pleted in 3 h with a low yield of 40% at room temperature with occasional stirring. To increase the yield of product, we took 1 mmol β -CD in 50 ml water at 60 °C. After a few minutes a clear solution was obtained into which again we added 1 mmol isatin and 2 moles of dimedone. At this time it took only 20 min for the reaction completion and the yield product was increased to 91%. The hydroxyl group present in the cavity of β -CD activates the carbonyl group of isatin, making it more susceptible to the attack of nucleophile. Thus the interaction that binds one molecule of dimedone and isatin becomes very fast. This step is the key step in the initiation of the reaction in terms of reduction of time and increase in yield. We also performed the reaction with α - and γ -cyclodextrin. We found that the best yield was obtained with β -cyclodextrin (Table 1, entry 2). Hence it was chosen as the phase transfer catalyst.

β -Cyclodextrin was recovered and reused. After each reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature β -cyclodextrin was filtered, washed with ice-cold

Table 1. Optimization of reaction conditions using different cyclodextrins^a

Entry	Catalyst	Yield (%) ^b
1	Water (without catalyst)	40
2	α -Cyclodextrin	30
3	β -Cyclodextrin	91
4	γ -Cyclodextrin	45

water and dried. When it was reused with the same substrate, we observed that its activity remained almost the same (Table 2).

In order to study the electronic effect of substituents

Table 2. Recyclability of β -CD

Cycles	(%) ^a	(%) ^b
0	91	85
1	89	82
2	87	80
3	85	78

^ais the yield of the product reuse of β -CD, ^bis the catalyst recovered by the reaction.

Table 3. Scope of various substrates in this synthesis (**3a-3h**)

Entry	1	2	3	Time ^a	Yield ^b
1				15	91
2				12	92
3				16	89

Table-3 (contd.)

4		14	91		
5		16	90		
6		15	89		
7		13	90		
8		14	91		

Synthesis of 3',3',6',6'-tetramethyl-3',4',6',7'-tetrahydrospiro[indoline-3,9'-xanthene]-1',2,8'(2'H,5'H)-trione, ^atime in minute, ^bis the isolated yield.

Table 4. Scope of same strategy with diversified aldehyde (3i-3p)

Entry	1	2	3	Time ^a	Yield ^b
1		12	90		
2		10	92		

Table-4 (contd.)

3		14	89		
4		14	90		
5		19	90		
6		14	88		
7		16	87		
8		20	86		

Synthesis of 3,3,6,6-tetramethyl-9-phenyl-3,4,5,6,7,9-hexahydro-1*H*-xanthene-1,8(2*H*)-dione and its derivatives, ^atime in minutes, ^bis isolated yield.

on the reaction, we concluded a series of experiments using different types of isatins and cyclic 1,3-diketone. Our next step to increase the range of this strategy by replacing the isatin with diversified aldehydes¹¹. We found that reaction ran very fast and that electron withdrawing groups present on aldehydes gave a higher yield in comparison to electron donating groups. The reaction run very fast (Table 4) electron withdrawing group present on aldehyde gives higher yield with comparison with having donating group. This strategy involved the formation of two C-C bond and one C-O bond for the synthesis of the desired product. Beauty of this protocol is that β -CD not only activates the reagents isatin, aldehydes and 1,3-cyclo diketones but also catalyses each step of the reaction.

Conclusion

To conclude, we have adopted a new route for the

synthesis of derivatives of 3',3',6',6'-tetramethyl-3',4',6',7'-tetrahydrospiro[indoline-3,9'-xanthene]-1',2,8'(2'*H*,5'*H*)-trione, 3,3,6,6-tetramethyl-9-phenyl-3,4,5,6,7,9-hexahydro-1*H*-xanthene-1,8(2*H*)-dione and its derivatives. The devised scheme has many significant features such as short reaction time, simple procedure, and atom economy.

General information

Reagents were obtained from commercial suppliers, and used without further purification unless otherwise specified by a reference. All reactions were performed using oven-dried glassware. Organic solutions were concentrated using a Buchi rotary evaporator. TLC was performed using silica gel GF254 (Merck) plates. Melting points were determined by open glass capillary method and are uncorrected. IR spectra in KBr were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 993 IR spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra were

recorded on a Bruker AVII 400 spectrometer in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal reference with chemical shift value being reported in ppm. All coupling constants (J) are reported in Hertz (Hz). ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on the same instrument at 100 MHz in CDCl_3 and TMS was used as internal reference. Mass (EI) spectra were recorded on a JEOL D-300 mass spectrometer. Elemental analyses were carried out in a Coleman automatic carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyzer.

General method

β -CD (1.0 mmol) was dissolved in water (25 ml) by warming to 55–60 °C until a clear solution was formed. Diversified isatin/aldehyde (1.0 mmol) was added, followed by 1,3-diketone (2.0 mmol) to the aqueous solution of β -CD. The mixture was stirred at 55–60 °C until the reaction was complete as monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC). After completion of the reaction, the mixture was cooled to room temperature and β -CD was filtered. The aqueous layer was extracted with ethyl acetate. The combined organic layers were extracted with water, saturated brine solution and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The solid product was formed no need of column chromatography.

Acknowledgement

We sincerely thank SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh, for providing micro-analyses and spectra. The authors are also thankful to UGC, New Delhi, for the award of Junior Research Fellowship (JRF).

Supplementary

3',3',6',6'-Tetramethyl-3',4',6',7'-tetrahydrospiro[indoline-3,9'-xanthene]-1',2,8'(2'H,5'H)-trione (**3a**) :

White solid; m.p. 304 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3420, 3053, 1725, 172; ^1H NMR (300 MHz CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 0.92 (6H, s), 0.98 (6H, s), 2.00, 2.15 (4H, J 12.1 Hz), 2.57 (4H, m), 6.71–7.05 (4H, m), 10.30 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 26.5, 28.6, 32.01, 40.7, 45.7, 50.8, 108.5, 113.5, 121.3, 122.7, 128.3, 134.5, 144.3,

164.05, 178.8, 195.7; EIMS 391 (M)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{25}\text{NO}_4$: C, 73.64; H, 6.44; N, 3.58. Found : C, 73.50; H, 6.45; N, 3.32%.

5-Bromo-3',3',6',6'-tetramethyl-3',4',6',7'-tetrahydrospiro[indoline-3,9'-xanthene]-1',2,8'(2'H,5'H)-trione (**3b**) :

White solid; m.p. 289 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3340, 2959, 1740, 1660, 1620; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ_{H} (ppm) : 1.06 (6H, s), 1.11 (6H, s), 2.17, 2.27 (4H, J 15.3 Hz), 2.46, 2.57 (4H, J 15.5 Hz), 6.71 (1H, d, J 5.2 Hz), 6.96 (1H, s), 7.24 (1H, d, J 5.4 Hz), 8.21 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_{C} (ppm) : 27.4, 28.6, 32.1, 41.3, 45.7, 50.8, 110.7, 113.3, 114.4, 125.6, 131.4, 135.7, 141.8, 163.8, 178.5, 195.7; EIMS 471 (M)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{24}\text{BrNO}_4$: C, 61.28; H, 5.14; N, 2.98. Found : C, 61.25; H, 5.02; N, 2.85%.

3',3',6',6'-Tetramethyl-5-nitro-3',4',6',7'-tetrahydrospiro[indoline-3,9'-xanthene]-1',2,8'(2'H,5'H)-trione (**3c**) :

Yellow solid; m.p. 2787 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3345, 2954, 1749, 1655; MS m/z : 436 (M)⁺; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ_{H} : 1.06 (6H, s), 1.15 (6H, s), 2.19, 2.30 (4H, J 15.9 Hz), 2.55, 2.61 (4H, J 16.6 Hz), 6.88 (1H, d, J 7.7 Hz), 7.81 (1H, s), 8.12 (1H, d, J 7.1 Hz), 8.86 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_{C} : 27.7, 28.4, 32.3, 41.4, 45.5, 50.7, 109.3, 112.7, 113.2, 125.8, 134.5, 142.8, 148.7, 164.5, 173.8, 195.7. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$: C, 66.04; H, 5.54; N, 6.42. Found : C, 65.74; H, 5.67; N, 6.20%.

1,3',3',6',6'-Pentamethyl-3',4',6',7'-tetrahydrospiro[indoline-3,9'-xanthene]-1',2,8'(2'H,5'H)-trione (**3e**) :

White solid; m.p. 305 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3045, 1738, 1724, 1580; MS m/z : 405 (M)⁺; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ_{H} (ppm) : 1.03 (6H, s), 1.13 (6H, s), 2.08, 2.21 (4H, J 15.1 Hz), 2.44, 2.56 (4H, J 15.6 Hz), 3.34, (3H, s), 6.82–7.24 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_{C} (ppm) : 26.6, 27.2, 29.3, 31.8, 41.4, 45.4, 50.8, 107.7, 113.5, 121.7,

121.8, 128.6, 133.02, 145.3, 163.6, 177.7, 195.5 . Anal. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₇NO₄ : C, 74.05; H, 6.71; N, 3.45. Found : C, 72.82; H, 6.46; N, 3.35%.

1,3',3',6',6'-Pentamethyl-3',4',6',7'-tetrahydrospiro[indoline-3,9'-xanthene]-1',2,8'(2'H,5'H)-trione (**3f**) :

White solid; m.p. 203 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3015, 1730, 1707, 1614; EIMS 419 (M)⁺; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ_H : 1.02 (6H, s), 1.11 (6H, s), 1.41 (3H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz), 2.07, 2.24 (4H, *J* 15.7 Hz), 2.44, 2.56 (4H, *J* 15.6 Hz), 3.86 (2H, t, *J* 6.7 Hz), 6.85–7.21 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ_C (ppm) : 11.9, 27.2, 29.2, 31.8, 35.1, 41.3, 45.5, 50.8, 107.9, 113.8, 121.7, 122.3, 128.5, 133.3, 144.4, 163.6, 177.1, 195.4 . Anal. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₉NO₄ : C, 74.44; H, 6.97; N, 3.34. Found : C, 74.40; H, 6.93; N, 3.35%.

1,3',3',6',6'-Pentamethyl-3',4',6',7'-tetrahydrospiro[indoline-3,9'-xanthene]-1',2,8'(2'H,5'H)-trione (**3g**) :

White powder; m.p. < 300 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3060, 2861, 1721, 1670, 1612; EIMS : 485 (M)⁺; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ_H : 1.04 (6H, s), 1.10 (6H, s), 2.16 (4H, m), 2.50 (4H, m), 3.29 (3H, s), 6.71–7.31 (3H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ_C : 26.76, 27.7, 28.6, 32.1, 41.3, 45.4, 50.8, 110.0, 113.2, 114.3, 125.3, 131.4, 134.8, 144.6, 163.10, 177.2, 195.7. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₆BrNO₄ : C, 61.99; H, 5.41; N, 2.89. Found : C, 61.8; H, 5.29; N, 2.71%.

3,3,6,6-Tetramethyl-9-phenyl-3,4,5,6,7,9-hexahydro-1*H*-xanthene-1,8(2*H*)-dione (**3h**) :

White solid; m.p. 205 °C; IR (KBr) : 2950, 1659, 1360, 1185 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.26–7.10 (5H, m), 4.75 (1H, s), 2.45 (4H, s), 2.20 (4H, q, *J* 16.5 Hz), 1.11 (6H, s), 0.99 (6H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 196.3, 162.4, 143.7, 128.6, 127.7, 115.3, 50.7, 40.5, 32.2, 31.7, 29.4, 27.3; EIMS 350 (M)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₃H₂₆O₃ : C, 78.83; H, 7.47. Found : C, 78.89; H, 7.55%.

3,3,6,6-Tetramethyl-9-(4-nitrophenyl)-3,4,5,6,7,9-hexahydro-1*H*-xanthene-1,8(2*H*)-dione (**3i**) :

White solid; m.p. 225 °C; IR (KBr) : 2948, 1677, 1655, 1528, 1359, 1212, 873 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 8.08 (d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.47 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 4.83 (1H, s), 2.47 (4H, s), 2.22 (4H, q, *J* 16.2 Hz), 1.13 (6H, s), 0.98 (6H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 196.3, 162.8, 151.4, 146.5, 129.6, 123.4, 114.6, 50.6, 40.7, 32.4, 32.2, 29.5, 29.3, 27.3; EIMS (*m/z*) : 395 (M)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₃H₂₅NO₅ : C, 69.85; H, 6.37; N, 3.54. Found : C, 69.81; H 6.30; N, 3.41%.

References

- (a) M. Srivastava, J. Singh, S. B. Singh, K. Tiwari, V. K. Pathak and J. Singh, *Green Chem.*, 2012, **14**, 901; (b) M. O. Simon and C. Jun Li, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2012, **41**, 1415; (c) D. Q. Xu, J. Wu, S. P. Luo, J. Zhang, J. Wu, X. Du and Z. Xu, *Green Chem.*, 2009, **11**, 1239; (d) Q. Zhang, B. Liu, W. Chen, Q. Lin and X. Lin, *Green Chem.*, 2008, **10**, 972; (e) J. Pinto, V. L. M. Silva, A. M. G. Silva, A. M. S. Silva, J. C. S. Costa, L. M. N. B. F. Santos, R. Enes, J. A. S. Cavaleiro, A. A. M. O. S. Vicented and J. A. C. Teixeira, *Green Chem.*, 2013, **15**, 970; (f) R. N. Butler, A. G. Coyne, W. J. Cunningham and E. M. Moloney, 2013, **78**, 3276; (g) C. Li and L. Chen, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2005.
- (a) K. Kalyanasundaram, "Photochemistry in Microheterogeneous Systems", Academic Press, San Diego, 1987; (b) A. Dandia, R. Singh, S. Bhaskaran and S. D. Samant, *Green Chem.*, 2011, **13**, 1852; (c) H. Tohma, S. Takizawa, H. Watanabe, Y. Fukuoka, T. Maegawa and Y. Kita, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1999, **64**, 3519; (d) S. Nigam, M. Belletete, R. S. Sarpalt and G. Durocher, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1995, **91**, 2133.
- (a) F. Hapiot, S. Tilloy and E. Monflier, *Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **106**, 767; (b) R. Villalonga, R. Cao and A. Fragoso, *Chem. Rev.*, 2007, **107**, 3088; (c) J. Szejtli, *Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **98**, 1743.
- W. Wen-Liang, Z. Tian-Jiao, T. Hong-Wen, L. Zhen-Yu, F. Yu-Chun, G. Qian-Qun and Z. Wei-Ming, *Chem. Biodivers.*, 2007, **4**, 2913.
- Y. Kyung Ho and O. Chang-Hyun, *Arch. Pharm.*, 2007, **340**, 530.
- O. Jolanta and K. Krzysztof, *Acta Pol. Pharm.*, 2006, **63**, 101; (b) K. Krzysztof, O. Jolanta and D. Malgorzata, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **43**, 53.
- M. S. Chande, R. S. Verma, P. A. Barve, R. R. Khanwelkar, R. B. Vaidya and K. B. Ajaikumar, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **40**, 1143.

8. R. Frank, M. Reich, R. Jostock, G. Bahrenberg, H. Schick and B. Henkel, US Pat 20080269271 (App. USPTO : 514278), 2008.
9. (a) A. Klasek, O. Rudolf, M. Rouchal, A. Lycka and A. Ruzicka, *Tetrahedron*, 2013, **69**, 492; (b) L. J. Zhang and C. G. Yan, *Tetrahedron*, 2013, **69**, 4915; (c) S. B. Singh, K. Tiwari, P. K. Verma, M. Srivastava, K. P. Tiwari and J. Singh, 2013, **25**, 255.
10. G. M. Ziarani, N. Lashgari and A.-R. Badiei, *Scientia Iranica (C)*, 2013, **20**, 580.
11. Girjesh K. Verma, Keshav Raghuvanshi, Rajiv K. Verma, Pratibha Dwivedi and M. S. Singh, *Tetrahedron*, 2011, **67**, 3698.